

used². The temperature sensor was a 10k Ω -thermistor and the calorimeter was calibrated electrically with the help of a manganin heater.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the heats of solution values. The average values for ΔH_1 in 1M- and 6M-HCl respectively are -46.1 ± 0.2 and -35.7 ± 0.5 kJ mol⁻¹. The average values for ΔH_2 in the corresponding acid solutions are -0.5 and -0.8 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The heat of solution of ThCl₄(c) in 1M- and 6M-HCl reported previously³ are -241.8 ± 0.7 and -188.3 ± 0.4 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively and ΔH_f° ThCl₄(c) also known from this latter source is -1184.4 ± 1.0 kJ mol⁻¹. The differential heat of formation of hydrochloric acid in 1M-HCl and 6M-HCl solutions are -164.4 ± 0.1 and -153.4 ± 0.2 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively³. The standard heat of formation of Th⁴⁺ in 1M- and 6M-HCl respectively are -768.6 ± 1.7 and -759.0 ± 0.8 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively³. From Cox and Pilcher⁴, ΔH_f° HAc(l) = -484.5 ± 2.0 kJ mol⁻¹. Substituting the above values in Eqs.(4) and (5), we get ΔH_f° ThAc₄(c) = -2662 ± 5 and -2665 ± 5 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The mean of the two values gives ΔH_f° ThAc₄(c) = -2663 ± 5 kJ mol⁻¹.

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Mössbauer Spectra of Tl(III) hexacyanoferrate(III)

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THE C \equiv N ligand very often gives rise to linkage isomerism yielding C bonded and N bonded metal complexes. Allen and Bonnet¹ observed that in samples of prussian blue containing various interstitial cations the flipping of CN ligand or

exchange of cations occurs around 250°. The phenomenon of cyanide linkage isomerism has also been investigated in iron(III) hexacyanochromate (III)² in which chromium(III) is associated with the C end of the ligands but even at room temperature the nature of bonding is found to change spontaneously yielding Fe(II) bonded through C holes and Cr(III) through N-holes. The identical structure of prussian blue and turnbull's blue³ has been explained on the basis of valence oscillation resonance between two structures in which the charge transfer from Fe³⁺ (high spin) to Fe²⁺ (low spin) or flipping of C \equiv N ligand occurs at the instant of combination.

In order to explore the phenomenon of linkage isomerism in double metal cyanide, we choose to examine the Mössbauer Spectra of a complex of iron(III) with Tl(III) where there is least possibility of electron transfer from one metal to the other. The results are reported in this short communication.

Experimental

Thallium(III) hexacyanoferrate (III) was prepared by double decomposition between Thallium(III) perchlorate and potassium ferricyanide. The hot concentrated solutions of the two reactants were mixed and heated to boiling. The dark blue precipitate was separated, washed several times with water, ethanol and finally with ether. The sample was dried in vacuum and its composition Tl [Fe(CN)₆] was established through elemental analysis. The I. R. spectrum of the sample was recorded in K Br between 4000 to 650 cm⁻¹ using Perkin-Elmer Spectrometer model-337 and a strong peak at 2100 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν C \equiv N is observed.

The Mössbauer spectra were recorded at room and liquid air temperatures on a spectrometer employing proportional counter, a single channel analyser and mechanical drive using constant velocity cams. The source used was ⁵⁷Co in Cu matrix.

Results and Discussion

The observed experimental results are summarized below :-

Chemical shift $\delta = +0.68$ mm/sec. (NP)

Quadrupole splitting $\Delta = 1.20$ mm/sec.

The Δ is almost temperature independent and the Mössbauer fraction is low at room temperature, as shown in the figure 1.

The observed chemical shift in the complex is around that reported for the highly ionic FeCl₃ and FeF₃. The value therefore suggests that Fe(III) in our complex is at least partly high spin which is improbable if the Fe is completely in the C-holes.

Fig. 1

A comparison of the observed Δ value with those of other heavy metal hexacyanoferrates(III) indicates an abnormally high value. Moreover Δ is temperature independent which is the characteristic of a high spin state. The abnormally high value of Δ suggests that all Fe(III) in the complex under investigation may not be in the low spin state and may be partly in the form of polarized Fe^{3+} . This is possible if we assume a resonance of the following type between two structure $Tl[Fe(CN)_6] \leftrightarrow Fe[Tl(CN)_6]$ in which Tl(III) has exchanged with Fe(III) in the coordination sphere. Such an exchange is likely to cause ligand isomerism, since Fe(III) has stronger tendency to bond through C while Thallium(III) prefers nitrogen bonding. Such a resonance having isocyanide structure will result in high distortion of the octahedral symmetry which will consequently increase the quadrupole splitting. It can therefore be safely concluded that there is a possibility of the co-existence of the high spin Fe^{3+} and the low spin Fe(III) in the complex, a conclusion reached earlier on the basis of Magnetic susceptibility measurements in the case of iron (II)-bis-(1, 10-phenanthroline)⁴. Moreover, the actual spectrum is an asymmetric doublets due to the superimposition of quadrupole doublets for the low spin Fe(III) and high spin Fe^{3+} and as such high value of Δ is observed similar to the case of prussian blue reported by Maer and Beasley⁵.

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Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes with N-N'-Diphenylthiocarbazide

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COMPLEXES of Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury(II) with sulphur ligands are of considerable interest as potential fungicides. Earlier complexes of substituted thiourea, dithiourea and mixed ligand complexes^{1,2} of thiourea and nitrogen bases have been reported. While studying complexes of d^{10} metal ions with sulphur ligands, ligands containing both sulphur and nitrogen donor sites aroused our interest. As a part of this programme, in recent communication, we have reported³⁻⁴ complexes of substituted thiocarbamides of divalent metal ions. In the present communication several Hg(II) and Cd(II) complexes with N-N'-diphenyl thiocarbazide have been described.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade. *Synthesis of the ligand*: Phenyl hydrazine (5.16 ml) was added slowly into a beaker containing carbon-disulphide (2 ml) kept in the freezing mixture when an exothermic reaction took place with the formation of white solid N-N'-diphenyl thiocarbazide. It was then recrystallized from rectified spirit when white crystalline compound separated out which was then filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Preparation of complexes: Ethanolic solution of metal halides were reacted separately with ethanolic solution of the ligand in 1 : 2 ratio and refluxed for 1 hr. On cooling white crystalline solid complexes separated out which were then filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Metal, sulfur and nitrogen in the complexes were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in $M/1000$ acetone solution of the complexes using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Beckman IR-20 and Perkin-Elmer-621 spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes reported in the present investigation have the general composition $[MLX_2]$, where $M = Cd(II)$, $Hg(II)$, X is Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- and L is N-N'-diphenyl thiocarbazide except the perchlorate complex which has the formula $[CdL_2]X_2$. These are white crystalline solids, have relatively low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium the Λ_M values are in the range of 8-12 mhos cm^2 indicating non-electrolytic nature of these complexes. Perchlorate complex has